

Integrating Concrete Examples into Thematic Maps of Social Inequalities: Assessing Public Perceptions

Rob Davidson*¹ and James Cheshire†

¹Department of Geography, UCL

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Summary

Maps can illustrate the extent of geographical health inequalities and the social determinants that shape them – factors like public transport, air pollution, and housing. Public health advocates have called for greater public engagement with the role that these social determinants play. This paper explores how different cartographic approaches, specifically the integration of person-centred examples within thematic maps, influence attitudes in this context. Using a randomised survey experiment ($N = 392$), we find few differences when analysing between subjects. However, within-subjects analysis found that exemplification was more persuasive, but only among audiences less confident in their ability to interpret charts and statistical maps.

KEYWORDS: data visualisation; vivid cartography; social determinants of health

Figure 1 Exemplification in the case of public transport, one of the social determinants of health. (1) adds a quote, and (2) adds data focused on an individual's story.

1. Introduction

Geographical health inequalities are shaped in part by the interactions between individuals and the

* rob.davidson.19@ucl.ac.uk

† james.cheshire@ucl.ac.uk

communities in which they live, work, and play. Public health advocates have called for greater communication on the role of these social determinants – the social, economic, and environmental factors that influence health. Maps are frequently used to communicate the extent of these inequalities as well as their causes, but there has been limited work to assess their efficacy in this context. This paper reports the results of a randomised survey experiment designed to understand how different cartographic approaches, specifically the integration of concrete examples focused on individuals, can change public perspectives.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Communicating the social determinants of health

In the UK, geographical health inequalities are widening, with life expectancy declining in some of the most deprived areas (Whitty, 2024). These inequalities are shaped in part by social determinants such as employment, housing, and the physical environment. While the public understand that the social determinants have a role to play (Smith & Anderson, 2018), there is a tendency to focus on individual behaviours instead (L'Hôte et al., 2018). So, there have been calls for greater public engagement with the social determinants (Whitty, 2024).

2.2. Exemplification

Studies in the fields of communication have assessed the relative persuasiveness of abstract quantitative information, concrete person-centred examples, and a combination of the two, in different circumstances (Hoeken & Hustinx, 2009). There is some evidence pointing to an exemplification effect, in which examples are more persuasive than abstract statistics because they are vivid and engaging (Zillmann & Brosius, 2000). Other studies presented narratives alongside data visualisations about the social determinants, finding that the abstract data reduced a tendency to perceive the narrative as cherry-picked (Niederdeppe et al., 2016). However, in cartography, the distinction between these two types of information is sometimes blurred, with individuals' stories used as a hook to illustrate quantitative information about their communities. Two examples of integrating individual stories into maps are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Left: a map combining satellite data and a family's testimony in Gaza (Saleh et al., 2024). Right: individuals used to illustrate what data points mean in an analysis of residential mobility (Kaysen & Singer, 2024).

This integration may be particularly useful when communicating about the social determinants of health, since the relationship between individuals and the communities in which they live is central to how they operate. Exemplification integrated into maps in this way may change policy attitudes, via greater engagement and comprehension, but it might also lead to perceptions of bias (it’s “just one person”). These effects may be moderated by users’ confidence or ability to interpret charts and maps (Aune & Hompland, 2024). Our randomised survey experiment tested these hypotheses.

3. Methods

We recruited 400 participants, a representative sample of the UK by age, gender, and political party affiliation, via Prolific. The procedure is shown in **Figure 3**. Participants were first presented with written background information on health inequalities. The main experiment followed this, in the form of information on three different social determinants. The Health Foundation group the determinants into six categories, and we included one topic from three of these categories.

First, participants were shown information on public transport, with an accompanying text focusing on how public transport affects employment opportunities, which affects health through chronic stress. The second topic was air pollution, which has a direct impact on health. The third topic was youth service provision, affecting health via community cohesion and reduced isolation.

For each topic, participants were randomly shown one of three maps, with varying levels of exemplification. Illustrations of this are shown in **Figure 1** and **Figure 4**. For the least exemplification, participants were shown a ‘community’ condition – a map of the social determinant at the local authority level. A ‘quotes’ condition added a description of a fictional character (although the quotes were real). Finally, an ‘individual’ condition had the most exemplification, adding an inset of the characters’ neighbourhood, providing more granular data in the process.

Figure 3 Study procedure.

After each topic, participants were asked a series of Likert-style questions. The main persuasion variable was captured with agreement that the issue should be a priority for national and local government, even if it involved raising taxes (or restrictions on motorists in the case of air pollution). We also measured if they perceived the issue as a severe problem, or linked to health inequalities, as well as whether they found the information engaging, trustworthy, and whether it incited defensive responses (if they found it ‘manipulative’ or ‘exaggerated’). Confidence in using charts and statistical maps was measured at the end of the survey.

We conducted two analyses. The first, a between-subjects analysis, examined responses topic-by-topic

to see the effect of exemplification. The second, a within-subjects analysis, made use of the multiple topics by examining changes in participants' responses. Responses here were centred on sample means for each topic to account for population-level differences in attitudes to the different topics. The independent variable for this analysis was *change in exemplification* between topics. **Table 1** in the appendix shows how this was derived.

Figure 4 Conditions for air pollution topic. (a) for 'community'; (b) for 'quotes'; (c) for 'individual'. Accompanying text not shown.

4. Results

The between-subjects analysis yielded very few significant results. The only statistically significant results were for the air pollution topic, in which the ‘individual’ condition had a small positive effect on *engagement* ($p < 0.05$) and *defensive responses* ($p < 0.05$). There were no interactions with *chart confidence*.

However, the within-subjects analysis found a positive effect on persuasion, at least for those with lower chart confidence. **Figure 5** shows the predicted change in responses from public transport to air pollution, by *change in exemplification* and *chart confidence*. Among those with lower-than-average confidence in using charts and statistical maps, greater exemplification was more persuasive, at least when considering the first two topics.

Predicted change in user responses (public transport to air pollution)

Chart confidence ● High ● Low

Figure 5 Predicted change in centred attitudes between the public transport and air pollution topics, with 95% BCa confidence intervals.

5. Discussion

Our results, in particular those from the between-subjects analysis, contribute to a growing number of studies finding little empirical support for the effects of visual storytelling techniques (Aune & Hompland, 2024; Liem et al., 2020).

However, the within-subjects analysis found some significant results, and we posit this may have been due to a priming effect. Since the questions remained broadly consistent between topics, participants may have been actively looking for differences between the information, reflected in changes to their responses. The interaction with *chart confidence* aligns with other studies finding that specific examples are disproportionately persuasive to those with less motivation or quantitative literacy (Cummins & Hahn, 2022; Gibson et al., 2011). This might be explained by those with lower chart confidence being more likely to rely on heuristics to process the information, such as the fact that there was visibly more information in the ‘individual’ conditions.

This study contributes to our understanding of how to communicate inequalities with maps, as well as to methodological debates in data visualisation research by highlighting differences in between- and within-subjects analyses. It also calls for an exploration into how different audiences react to forms of cartographic persuasion. Future research might involve testing maps that present more than one variable.

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Biographies

Rob Davidson is a PhD candidate in the Geography Department at UCL and a PGTA in the Department of Political Science. His research concerns data visualisation, health inequalities, and policy.

James Cheshire is Professor of Geographic Information and Cartography at UCL, Director of the UCL Social Data Institute and Deputy Director of the ESRC Consumer Data Research Centre.

Appendix

Table 1 Deriving *change in exemplification* score from the map conditions, in this case for public transport and air pollution.

Transport	Pollution	Change in exemplification
Community	Quotes	+1
Community	Individual	+2
Quotes	Individual	+1
Individual	Quotes	-1
Individual	Community	-2
Quotes	Community	-1
Individual	Individual	0
Quotes	Quotes	0
Community	Community	0

Figure 6 Structural equation model for the within-subjects analysis for public transport and air pollution, with path coefficients. Here, chart confidence is in its granular, seven-point scale.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$